

The Effect of HRIS on Innovation Capability of HR Employee and the Moderating Role of Affective Commitment

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ABSTRACT: The current study aims to evaluate the influence of utilizing Human Resources Information Systems (HRIS) in the human resource (HR) departments on the innovation capacity of employees who are working in Malaysian companies. The research model and related hypotheses were examined on over 186 HR employees in Malaysian companies. The findings of this study have been assessed through Smart PLS software, which revealed that utilizing HRIS has a significant impact on the HR innovation capacity. Besides, Malaysian HR employees have shown that there is a positive correlation between implementing HRIS and employee innovation capacity, which can be moderated by affective commitment. Effectively speaking, the HRIS is more noteworthy and has a significant impact on HR employees' innovation while they engage more with the organization. This study tries to introduce factors that are effective to enhance employees' innovation.

KEYWORDS: HRIS implementation; human resource management; commitment; innovation

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of globalization leads to a competitive international environment and in order to survive in this area, companies should equip themselves with consistent and reliable information systems to monitor all their activities. It is very difficult to manage a huge amount of information in a company that comes from different sources through traditional (non-integrated) information systems. Therefore, companies are pushed to adopt updated and developed information systems to share data and provide a knowledge platform to integrate all information from various parts of the company as finance, manufacturing, human resources, etc. (Liang et al., 2007; Ngai et al., 2008). This information helps the company stave in making decisions as it produces knowledge that leads to competitive advantages for the organization (Camisón-Haba et al., 2019). Malaysian companies like other international companies started to make an effort to change their working methods and adjust themselves to this uncertain and competitive environment from January, 1996 (Shahreki et al., 2019). Malaysian SMEs are keen on implementing new information systems such as Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) to endure in this competitive environment.

In other words, human capital plays a significant role in a company's success and development (Angrist et al., 2021; Manuelli & Seshadri, 2014). According to Wright and McMahan (2011), human capital represents the creativity, skill, knowledge, and health of the employees. Accordingly, higher human capital enhances the employees' learning capacity which leads to improvement of employees' innovative capacity (McGuirk et al., 2015). Hence, to develop this valuable human capital, the companies' managements ought to consider the HR management function such as training, recruitment, remunerations, etc., that can be facilitated through the HRIS acquisition. Through the reviews of the literature, the HR collection of technological innovations is categorized as virtual human resources groups (VHR), HRIS, and electronic human resources (e-HR) (Marler & Fisher, 2013; Shahreki, 2019a). Developing the HR function leads to various services enhancement as it is offered to share implied information throughout the organization and accompanies with the whole functionality of relatively a strategic dimension (Farndale et al., 2010; Ibrahim et al., 2020; Shahreki et al., 2022).

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Moreover, HR functions are being developed and updated through the HRIS contribution. Strohmeier (2020) proposes that the triple influence of using information and communication technology (ICT) on the HR task and findings revealed that HRIS has an impact on the HR function in relational and operational ways. Bondarouk et al. (2017) and Shahreki, Jamaluddin, et al. (2020) also support this result and reported that the functional influences can be added to enhance HR employees' productivity. HRIS plays an essential role in the HR function's success and leads to accurate and precise employee performance (Maamari & Osta, 2021; Marler & Parry, 2016; Shahreki, 2019b).

According to Strohmeier (2007), the HRIS benefits are facilitating access to information, increased speed of response, administrative efficiency, and improved decision-making and reporting. HRIS also influences the HR operational and strategic management (Stone & Dulebohn, 2013). Companies should utilize the most complicated technological equipment and systems to enhance the performance of employees. For more confirmation, there are many research shows the role of HRIS in enhancing employee performance and productivity (Bondarouk & Ruel, 2009; Marler & Fisher, 2013; Shahreki, 2024b; Shahreki et al., 2023; Shahreki et al., 2021; Stone et al., 2015; Stone & Dulebohn, 2013; Strohmeier, 2007). Commitment can be categorized as continuity commitment, affective commitment, and normative commitment (Meyer & Herscovitch, 2001).

According to Meyer et al. (2002), normative commitment means staying in the organization. Continuity commitment is related to the activity interruption and is a psychological state. It can be a result of a shortage of employees' comparison if they leave the organization. Finally, the employee's positive feeling toward the organization is affective commitment, which is determined by the necessity of the employees' contribution or sacrifice themselves to benefit the organization. In the current paper, only affective commitment is considered as it is the foundation of the other two dimensions. Affective commitment is the heart of organizational commitment (Pierro et al., 2013), and it plays an important role in the ERP project success and the HRIS module. Effectively speaking, it enables the adoption and especially the use of IS that increases the employees' innovative capacity and it gives a fairly ERP high failure rate (Bai & Sarkis, 2013; Roglinger et al., 2012). Therefore, HRIS usage should be being go together with an employee's affective engagement to guarantee a greater chance of improving innovation capacity. This research aims to evaluate the influence of HRIS on employee attitudes to reveal numerous advantages that an organization can produce. Although HRIS has a positive effect on employees, it increases their performance and enhances their creativity (Ruel et al., 2007), which is the first step in innovation development (Forsman, 2011). All in all, HRIS is considered a useful tool in many research (Maamari & Osta, 2021; Parry, 2011; Troshani et al., 2011).

These researchers also emphasized on all benefits, such as deduced time to complete tasks, easy access to HRIS, and improved planning programs (Marler & Fisher, 2013; Marler & Parry, 2016; Shahreki, 2024a; Strohmeier, 2007). Though, there is limited studies have been carried out to investigate the usage of HRIS and employee innovation capacity development. This research aims to evaluate the moderating impact of affective commitment on the relationship between the employees' innovation capacity and HRIS usage. Even though Chin et al. (2003) and Ramírez-Correa et al. (2019) carried out some studies on information system and used some models with moderators, this study elaborates this line of research more and facilitate the management.

In summary, there is limited research focused on the relationship between HRIS implementation and the innovation capacity of HR employees by moderating effect of "affective commitment". Therefore, the current research objectives are evaluating the HRIS utilization effect on increasing the employees' innovation capacity by moderating effect of "affective commitment". To do this, in the next section, the reviews of literature on HRIS and other research disciplines will be discussed. The research model will be developed and examined over a practical study on a sample of Malaysian companies, which will be followed by findings, results, and limitations of this research.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 HRIS

Human resource information system (HRIS) is comprised of software, staff, materials, data, and proceedings (Bondarouk et al., 2017; Shahreki & Lee, 2024; Stone & Dulebohn, 2013). Using HRIS in the HR section revealed many advantages as deducing client request time performance, industrializing HR function tasks and routine functions, developing HR quality service, and developing operations efficiency (Bondarouk & Ruel, 2009; Shahreki & Lee, 2024; Strohmeier, 2007) enhancing employee knowledge and productivity (Parry, 2011; Troshani et al., 2011). There are several studies have shown the advantages of HRIS usage and adoption for employees and organizations (Ibrahim et al., 2022; Marler & Fisher, 2013; Shahreki et al., 2019; Shahreki & Nakanishi, 2016; Shahreki, Nakanishi, et al., 2020; Stone & Dulebohn, 2013).

HRIS adoption facilitates and develops organizational routine, and creates strong communication between employees and top management; it provides applicable data and information that is considered as a foundation of organizational decisions making (Florkowski & Olivas-Lujan, 2006; Marler & Parry, 2016; Stone et al., 2015). Implementing of HRIS, supports the HR department to decrease their daily performance that leads to their organizational strategic decisions (Johnson et al., 2016; Ruel et al., 2007;

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Strohmeier, 2020). The reviews of literature point out the role of information technology (IT) and information systems (IS) in the improvement of employees' performances (Holden & Karsh, 2010; Parry, 2011), and enhancing their innovation capacity (Forsman, 2011; McGuirk et al., 2015).

2.2 HRIS implementation and innovation capacity

Nowadays, creativity is a key factor in companies' success (Escrig-Tena et al., 2018; McGuirk et al., 2015) and helps to increase the company's functions (Camisón-Haba et al., 2019). According to resources theory, each employee represents a sacred source of a company so he/she plays an important role in the formation of innovation (Abdullah et al., 2016). In the innovation process, the employees' creativity is the first step (Florkowski & Olivás-Lujan, 2006) to ensure the transmission of innovation throughout the organization (Forsman, 2011). Ferreira et al. (2020) defined innovation capacity as "an emotional and a cognitive process relative to creativity." Hughes et al. (2018) proposed that individual innovation or creativity as "Novel and useful ideas, processes or products offered by an employee, as judged by relevant others." Effectively speaking, individual innovation or general innovation requires a well-determined prerequisite and should be suitable. In other words, innovation can be a process of ideas deviation to find a suitable solution (Amabile & Pratt, 2016). The reviews of literature revealed that the innovation capacity of each person under different viewpoints. There are some research has been conducted on the creativity and introduced it as an important factor in innovation (Lee et al., 2020; Oman et al., 2013; Saroghi et al., 2015; Squalli & Wilson, 2014). Therefore, companies should persuade their employees to be more innovative by implementing suitable systems (Auernhammer & Hall, 2013). On another hand, they should make an effort to make this individual innovation capacity enhancement as a permanent process (Cerne et al., 2013) that requires the contribution of managers in the learning process, and planning suitable policies such as the implementing of available resources.

The majority of studies that have been done before, focus on influential factors to increase individual creativity such as transformational leadership with front-line that has an important influence on the creativity of employees (Hughes et al., 2018). According to Mekler et al. (2017), motivation as an intrinsic motivation is the most influential factor on creativity and the dimension of 'opening up to experience' that has a positive and direct impact on it. Zhang et al. (2020) proposed that self-leadership as another influential factor on creativity that results to individual innovation. All in all, creativity and self-leadership are requirements of innovation. The implementation of HRIS significantly boosts the innovation capacity of HR employees, transforming HR into a strategic partner within the organization. By automating routine tasks, HRIS allows HR employees to focus on high-value activities, fostering a culture of continuous improvement and innovation. The data-driven insights provided by HRIS empower HR professionals to make informed decisions, predict future trends, and develop proactive strategies that align with organizational goals (Noutsas et al., 2017; Shahreki, 2024c; Shahreki & Lee, 2024). Improved communication and collaboration tools within HRIS facilitate the sharing of ideas and collective problem-solving, which are crucial for driving innovation. Enhanced employee experiences through self-service options and streamlined processes not only boost employee satisfaction but also allow HR employees to concentrate on developing innovative programs that enhance workplace culture and engagement (Jiakui et al., 2023; Klimovskikh et al., 2023; Shahreki, 2024b; Shahreki et al., 2023).

Effective talent management and development enabled by HRIS ensure that high-potential employees are identified and nurtured, fostering a culture of continuous learning and innovation. The system's ability to ensure compliance and manage risks efficiently further allows HR employees to focus on strategic initiatives rather than administrative burdens (Shahreki, 2024a; Shahreki et al., 2024; Shin et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2022). Strategic workforce planning supported by HRIS provides valuable insights into workforce demographics and skills gaps, allowing HR professionals to develop innovative strategies for workforce development. Continuous improvement and feedback mechanisms within HRIS enable HR employees to identify areas for improvement and implement solutions that enhance performance and satisfaction (Shahreki et al., 2019; Shahreki & Ghanad, 2023; Xie et al., 2021; Zweifel, 2021).

Integration with other business systems ensures a seamless flow of information across the organization, enabling HR employees to develop innovative cross-functional initiatives that drive organizational success. Additionally, the ability to leverage advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence and machine learning within HRIS further enhances the capacity for innovation by providing predictive analytics and personalized employee experiences (Chege et al., 2020; Heidenreich & Talke, 2020; Lee et al., 2020; Shahreki & Lee, 2024). HRIS transforms the role of HR employees from administrative support to strategic partners, enabling them to drive innovation and contribute significantly to the organization's overall success. By leveraging the capabilities of HRIS, HR professionals can develop and implement innovative HR practices that align with the dynamic needs of the business, ultimately fostering a more agile, responsive, and competitive organization (Camisón-Haba et al., 2019; Galanaki et al., 2019; Min et al., 2019; Park et al., 2019; Shahreki, 2024c; Shahreki & Lee, 2024).

On the other hand, there are many research that pointed out the nature of the relationship between individual innovation capacity

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and HRIS usage (Francis et al., 2014; Gurusinghe et al., 2021; Schalk et al., 2013; Xie et al., 2021). Information technology (IT) is a significant tool to develop and increase operational efficiency since it helps to share and transfer knowledge to produce creative ideas (Lei et al., 2021; Zweifel, 2021). Besides, according to Chege et al. (2020), using IT provides conditions to enhance and promote individuals' innovation to do their jobs perfectly and generate creative ideas. The current study aims to examine the decisive role of various tools, IT, and their functions in the formation of new ideas and the use of them in an innovative product. In summary, this access to new information equip the employees with new methods and planning (Sahay & Walsham, 2017), and using computer promote this individual creativity. According to all the above discussions, the following hypothesis are being formulated:

H1. Implementation of HRIS enhance innovation capacity of HR employee.

2.3 Affective commitment as a moderate

Affective commitment can be defined as an employee relationship with the organization (Matzler & Renzl, 2007) that is considered to what extend they want to be engaged in the organization. Effectively speaking, the employees' identification and their engagement degree to the organization can be empowered by the consistent relationship between the organization's values and the employee's values. Therefore, affective commitment decreases the employees' absence from work and enhance their organizational performance and citizenship behavior (Ernsting et al., 2013; Gellatly & Withey, 2012).

In general, there are three influential factors in organizational commitment as organizational characteristics, work experience, and employee demographics (Alqudah et al., 2022). The complete employees' commitment is needed to digitalize the HR management function (Tang & Vandenberghe, 2020), which is very crucial, although, its successfulness depends on the employees' accessibility and their tendency to implement it (Lin et al., 2018). On the other hand, this degree of commitment has a positive effect on employees' innovation capacity (Zhang et al., 2022). In other words, higher employees' commitment leads to more implementation of new technologies in organizations (García-Cruz et al., 2018). However, the employees' resistance to change can lead to the failure of implementing new technologies (Haep, 2021).

This study assumes that an employee's innovation capacity is related to his/her involvement and commitment to the organization and being creative only accrued when the employee feels comfortable in the organization. Thus, engaging employees in the organization's vision pursue them to adopt the new strategies and be active in decision-making processes (Lee et al., 2020). Effectively speaking, the role of commitment in employees' motivation and enhancing their performance has been discussed in many studies (E-vahdati et al., 2023; Hashemi et al., 2023; Ibrahim et al., 2020; Loor-Zambrano et al., 2022; Mgammal & Al-Matari, 2021; Nguyen et al., 2021; Nha Trang et al., 2022; Shahreki, Ganesan, et al., 2020), while this motivation improving the creativity (Amabile & Pratt, 2016; Oman et al., 2013). Commitment can be considered as an influential factor in enhancing the employees' creativity and employee and organizational innovation (Matzler & Renzl, 2007). Affective commitment helps organizational citizenship behavior, which enhances organizational effectiveness, innovation, and efficiency (Gellatly & Withey, 2012). The commitment of staff to the organization also effects on innovation capacity improvement (García-Cruz et al., 2018; Tang & Vandenberghe, 2020). Affective commitment significantly enhances the impact of HRIS implementation on HR employee innovation capacity. This emotional bond between employees and their organization acts as a powerful catalyst, amplifying the advantages of HRIS by fostering greater creativity, engagement, and strategic alignment within the HR department (Alqudah et al., 2022; Shahreki & Lee, 2024; Shahreki et al., 2024; Tang & Vandenberghe, 2020). When employees are emotionally committed to their organization, they are more likely to embrace and effectively use new technologies, such as HRIS. This positive attitude and willingness to adapt to technological advancements result in more innovative practices within HR. For instance, HR professionals can leverage HRIS to analyze employee data more comprehensively, leading to better talent management, improved performance evaluations, and the development of personalized training programs. These innovations not only enhance HR functions but also contribute to overall organizational success (García-Cruz et al., 2018; Lin et al., 2018; Shahreki, 2024a).

Organizations that cultivate affective commitment among their employees can fully exploit the potential of HRIS to drive innovation. Employees who feel a strong emotional connection to their organization are more motivated to use HRIS tools to their fullest potential. This motivation translates into higher levels of engagement, where employees actively seek out new ways to improve processes, solve problems, and implement creative solutions. Such an environment encourages continuous improvement and fosters a culture of innovation (Ernsting et al., 2013; Gellatly & Withey, 2012; Sanders et al., 2008). Furthermore, affective commitment ensures that HR professionals are aligned with the strategic goals of the organization. This alignment is crucial for developing and executing strategies that support long-term success. HRIS provides the necessary data and tools for strategic workforce planning, enabling HR professionals to make informed decisions about recruitment, retention, and development. By integrating HRIS into their strategic planning, organizations can better anticipate future needs, address skill gaps, and ensure that their workforce is prepared to meet emerging challenges (Matzler & Renzl, 2007; Meyer et al., 2002; Shahreki, 2024b; Shahreki &

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Ghanad, 2023).

Improving the employee experience is another significant benefit of combining HRIS implementation with affective commitment. HRIS offers self-service options and streamlined processes that enhance efficiency and reduce administrative burdens. This efficiency allows HR employees to focus on more strategic and innovative tasks, such as developing programs to boost employee engagement and satisfaction. A positive employee experience, in turn, reinforces affective commitment, creating a virtuous cycle that further enhances innovation capacity (Alqudah et al., 2022; Shahreki et al., 2019; Shahreki & Lee, 2024; Tang & Vandenberghe, 2020). Moreover, the integration of HRIS with other business systems facilitates seamless information flow across the organization. This integration enables HR professionals to collaborate more effectively with other departments, leading to the development of cross-functional initiatives that drive organizational success. For example, HR can work closely with finance to develop compensation strategies that attract and retain top talent, or with IT to implement technologies that support remote work and flexible scheduling (García-Cruz et al., 2018; Lin et al., 2018; Shahreki et al., 2023; Shahreki et al., 2019).

The adoption of advanced technologies, such as artificial intelligence and machine learning, within HRIS further enhances the capacity for innovation. These technologies provide predictive analytics that can forecast workforce trends, identify potential issues before they arise, and offer personalized recommendations for employee development. By leveraging these capabilities, HR professionals can create more targeted and effective strategies, ensuring that the organization remains agile and competitive in a rapidly evolving business environment (Jiakui et al., 2023; Klimovskikh et al., 2023; Shahreki & Lee, 2024; Zhang et al., 2022). Affective commitment plays a crucial role in enhancing the relationship between HRIS implementation and HR employee innovation capacity. It serves as a catalyst, amplifying the benefits of HRIS and driving greater creativity, engagement, and strategic alignment within the HR function. Organizations that nurture a culture of emotional commitment and invest in advanced HR technologies are well-positioned to thrive. By fully leveraging the capabilities of HRIS, these organizations can develop and implement innovative HR practices that align with the dynamic needs of the business, ultimately fostering a more agile, responsive, and competitive organization (Lin et al., 2018; Shahreki et al., 2019; Shin et al., 2022; Tang & Vandenberghe, 2020; Zweifel, 2021). Effectively speaking, according to Meyer and Herscovitch (2001), the greater commitment of employees to the organization results in emotional affection for a company and continue to be members of the organization contributing to the company's achievement. Accordingly, the effective commitment of employees to the organization is developed by HRIS implementation which can be considered as an opportunity to enhance the organizational function. As a result, the researcher can propose that the employees' affective commitment leads to their innovation capacity enhancement so that the following hypothesis is reformulated. We propose (also see Figure 1):

H2. Affective commitment exerts a stronger effect on the relation of HRIS implementation and HR employee innovation capacity.

FIGURE. 1. Conceptual model

3. METHODOLOGY

In this section, the usage methodology is discussed which contains administering SMEs questionnaires that use HRIS in the HR department of Malaysian companies. These Malaysian companies are active in different sectors and can be categorized into service and industry. In the current study, a convenience sampling method is adopted from other studies. A number of 300 questionnaires were sent to 75 Malaysian SMEs, where the HR department uses HRIS such as HR management, human resource development, recruitment manager, training officers, HR team, and the performance evaluation manager and all are located in Malaysia. Based on the findings, only 66 SMEs out of 195 respondents replied. Nine questionnaires were omitted during data processing so only 186 questionnaires were remained with a 62% return rate. In the current study, implementation of HRIS was measured through usage frequency on a 7-item scale (Ruel & Van der Kaap, 2012; Shahreki et al., 2019; Straub et al., 1995), and

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innovation capacity was measured through 3 items scale, which was adopted from (Hussain et al., 2007), (Appendix 1). Lastly, Allen and Meyer (1990)'s edited version of the scale was modified with 4 items to measure "affective commitment". A 5-point Likert scale was used to measure the three constructs of our study model, which range from very low to very strong. Besides, the PLS was used for testing the hypotheses and SPSS software was used to validate our scales (Ringle et al., 2020).

3.1. The descriptive statistics of sample

Analysis of respondents' demographics revealed that 68.8% of respondents were male (31.2% female), 64% were bachelor's degree, and 45.2% were 30-40 years old. Moreover, 81.2% were managers, and 66.1% more than four years used HRIS (see Table 1).

Table 1. Respondents' Demographic

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	128	68.8
	Female	58	31.2
Education	Certificate/diploma	32	17.2
	Bachelor degree	119	64.0
	Master degree	28	15.1
	PhD	7	3.8
Age	Under 30	36	19.4
	30-40	84	45.2
	41-50	54	29.0
	Above 51	12	6.5
Job	Manager	151	81.2
	Executive	28	15.1
	Others	7	3.8
HRIS utilization	"Less than two years"	8	4.3
	"Between two and four years"	48	25.8
	"More than four years"	123	66.1
	Others	7	3.8

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics and differences in the HRIS implementation. The Malaysian SMEs employees utilize the 7 HRIS functionalities in different grades.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics in the HRIS implementation

HRIS Implementation	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	S.D
1 Core HR	3	5	4.28	0.811
2 Payroll	3	5	4.11	0.933
3 Employee Benefits	3	5	3.89	0.934
4 Training	3	5	3.62	1.122
5 Performance Management	3	5	3.37	1.361
6 Time Tracking and Leave	3	5	3.42	1.213
7 Onboarding	3	5	3.01	0.912

These Malaysian sample companies implement the HRIS module in Core HR (mean = 4.28), payroll (mean = 4.11), Employee Benefits (mean = 3.89), Training (mean = 3.62), Performance Management (mean = 3.37), and Time Tracking and Leave (mean = 3.42). In contrast, the Malaysian SMEs employees rarely used Onboarding (mean = 3.01). In addition, the results of PLS reveal that the items are homogeneous. Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability for all constructs were more than 0.7, and the average variance extracted is more than 0.5. In addition, loading was more than 0.5, also the Skewness and Kurtosis test shows that data

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are normally distributed (Hair et al., 2019), (see Table 3). Based on the results of Table 4, the Constructs' discriminant validity shows that it supports the validity of the measurement model (Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Hair et al., 2019).

Table 3. Construct Reliability and Validity

Constructs and Items	Loading>0.5	CR>0.7	AVE>0.5	$\alpha >0.7$	S	K
Implementation of HRIS		0.960	0.777	0.951		
IM1	0.924				0.232	0.426
IM2	0.915				-0.238	-0.911
IM3	0.813				-0.432	-0.302
IM4	0.757				-0.152	-0.441
IM5	0.947				-0.343	-0.611
IM6	0.878				-0.482	-0.783
IM7	0.922				-0.275	1.954
HR Staff Innovation Capacity		0.954	0.873	0.927		
IC1	0.899				-0.336	-0.647
IC2	0.971				0.347	-0.915
IC3	0.931				-0.752	-0.939
Affective Commitment		0.953	0.837	0.934		
AC1	0.843				0.812	1.545
AC2	0.962				-0.634	-0.246
AC3	0.944				-0.265	0.946
AC4	0.905				-0.287	-0.752

Note: α = "Cronbach's alpha"; AVE = "average variance extracted"; CR = "composite reliability"; S = Skewness; K = Kurtosis.

Table 4. Constructs' discriminant validity

	1	2	3
1 Implementation of HRIS	0.853		
2 HR Staff Innovation Capacity	0.677	0.856	
3 Affective Commitment	0.552	0.623	0.816

Notes: N=186; Diagonal measures (bold) are the square root of the "average variance extracted" (AVE) for every construct.

Table 5. Test with PLS (direct relation without moderator)

Path	t-Statistics	R ²	Coefficient (β)
HRIS Implementation -> Innovation Capacity	8.015	0.375	0.581

Table 6. Test with PLS after including Moderator

Path	t-Statistics	R ²
HRIS Implementation -> Innovation Capacity	5.271	0.521
HRIS Implementation -> Affective Commitment -> Innovation Capacity	3.265	

4. DISCUSSIONS

This study measured the nature of the relationship between HR staff innovation capacity and HRIS implementation and examined the moderating effect of this relationship. The findings of our research revealed that applying various HRIS features tends to foster the improvement of the innovation capacity of HR employees. This result has been achieved through the interviews that have been conducted by HR employees, which is in line with the results of Hughes et al. (2018), Kleis et al. (2012), Shahreki et al. (2019) and Lee et al. (2020) studies. On the other hand, according to the data collection, the relationship between the innovation capacity of HR employees and HRIS implementation moderated by affective commitment is supported by Khan et al. (2011) results. He proposed that the commitment of employees leads to increasing their satisfaction and creativity. Effectively speaking, affective

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commitment of employees encourages each employee's creativity to bring new ideas and knowledge to the organization's performance.

The findings of current research support other related studies that surveyed information systems with the use of moderating factors. Besides, these findings are beneficial for SMEs of Malaysian companies to do investment in ICT to develop. In other words, applying HRIS in Malaysian companies facilitates HR department performance and improves their innovation capacity. Affective commitment is another factor to optimize the creativity of employees that carries new strategies and enhances their performance. The integration of HRIS implementation and affective commitment increases the employees' creativity.

Managers should encourage HR employees to apply HRIS and use affective commitment as moderator. The findings of the current study help HR managers to envision the advantages of applying HRIS to enhance their company's performance. The usage of HRIS also helps HR employees' innovation capacity improvement and develop service quality. Effectively speaking, careful employment of HRIS should be planned and followed by the HR department and HR management to achieve the goals of the organization. HRIS industrializes administrative tasks, facilitates the HR function, reduces costs, abolishes duplicate tasks, and enhances service quality.

The findings of this study are a good resource to encourage managers to apply HRIS and implement it in the company which is supported by Troshani et al. (2011) results. Its compatibility and adoption enhance the employees' productivity, their innovation capacity, and service quality. On the other hand, the help of management was a crucial factor that errand the enhancement of employees' commitment and the improvement of their organizational skills and helped us to achieve the results of the current study. Effectively speaking, the innovation capacity is enhanced while the implementation of HRIS is combined with employees' affective commitment. However, the affective commitment decreases employees' resistance to change, while in ERP projects, this resistance is mostly considered as a failure source.

Although the results of the current study are useful for consultants, managers, and for employees who are interested in gathering information for enhancing their performance, it has some limitations. The first limitation of this study was the sample size, which was quite small (186 participants). Another limitation was related to some items in this study questionnaire such as position, age, and level of study. The last limitation was on the data collection that only used the exploratory analysis. In summary, there are some suggestions for further research. Further studies should consider these standard data to examine if they affect the respondents' contribution. Besides, the relationship between employee productivity and HRIS implementation, the relationship between the HR service quality and HRIS implementation, or the relationship between HRIS implementation and other variables simultaneously can be discussed in further research. The relationship between the innovation capacity of employees and HRIS implementation can be affected by organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) also can be an interesting topic for future work. Finally, the findings of current research also can be duplicated as a comprehensive qualitative case study where HRIS will be thoroughly used.

5. CONCLUSION

This study attempts to examine HRIS implementation's impact on increasing the employees' innovation capacity and examine the moderating influence of affective commitment on this relationship. To do this, the first hypothesis testing revealed that coefficient = 0.581, $P < 0.01$, and R^2 is 0.375. Moreover, the Smart PLS software Bootstrap was applied to measure the importance of their relationship.

Based on Table 5, the t-statistic is $8.015 > 1.96$, that shows the relationship was significant. It also explains that 37.5% of the discrepancy in the HR staff innovation capacity was improved. Therefore, while more HR employees implement HRIS in their workplace performance leads to their innovation capacity improvement so hypothesis 1 is accepted.

As a matter of fact, the HRIS implementation reduces costs by reducing task performance time besides reducing paperwork and HR employees. HRIS implementation enhances planning and programming development, stimulates employee interaction, and improves employees' knowledge by the knowledge management circulate that flows all over the organization and provender all departments. All in all, it enhances organizational performance, improves communication between top employees and management, and provides applicable information and data as a foundation for making decisions throughout the company (Johnson et al., 2016; Maamari & Osta, 2021; Shahreki et al., 2019). In conclusion, the HRIS adoption helps HR employees to work effectively and facilitates the general company's development. HRIS adoption also persuades top management to keep the operational staff and plan for all upcoming projects. It generated a dashboard that is followed up automatically in specific applications and observing the growth and safety in work situations. It detected the repetitive absences in the department to identify their causes and find solutions for that quickly. This information helps employees and managers to reply to changes more quickly.

Table 6 shows the hypothesis number result. This table revealed the relationship between HR staff innovation capacity and HRIS

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implementation is significant with the existence of the “affective commitment” as a moderator variable. The T-value of hypothesis 1 is 5.271 in the moderator so the first hypothesis is accepted. The coefficient of hypothesis 1 determination before ($R^2= 0.375$) and after ($R^2= 0.521$) presence of the “affective commitment” as a moderator has shown that R^2 has improved.

All in all, the Bootstrap procedure results with a t-statistic of (3.265 > 1.96) shows that there is a relationship. Effectively speaking, the affective commitment moderates the relationship between HR staff innovation capacity and HRIS implementation and when affective commitment is strong, this relationship is strong. Accordingly, the second hypothesis also is accepted. In an HRIS implementation, affective commitment improves the employees’ innovation capacity since they pursue to apply new creative ideas to their company.

REFERENCES

- 1) Abdullah, I., Omar, R., & Panatik, S. A. (2016). A Literature Review on Personality, Creativity and Innovative Behavior. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 6(1), 177-182.
- 2) Allen, N. J., & Meyer, J. P. (1990). The measurement and antecedents of affective, continuance and normative commitment to the organization. *Journal of occupational psychology*, 63(1), 1-18.
- 3) Alqudah, I. H. A., Carballo-Penela, A., & Ruza-Sanmartín, E. (2022). High-performance human resource management practices and readiness for change: An integrative model including affective commitment, employees’ performance, and the moderating role of hierarchy culture. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 28(1), 100177. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iedeen.2021.100177>
- 4) Amabile, T. M., & Pratt, M. G. (2016). The dynamic componential model of creativity and innovation in organizations: Making progress, making meaning. *Research in Organizational Behavior*, 36(1), 157-183. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.riob.2016.10.001>
- 5) Angrist, N., Djankov, S., Goldberg, P. K., & Patrinos, H. A. (2021). Measuring human capital using global learning data. *Nature*, 592(7854), 403-408.
- 6) Auernhammer, J., & Hall, H. (2013). Organizational culture in knowledge creation, creativity and innovation: Towards the Freiraum model. *Journal of Information Science*, 40(2), 154-166. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0165551513508356>
- 7) Bai, C., & Sarkis, J. (2013). A grey-based DEMATEL model for evaluating business process management critical success factors. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 146(1), 281-292.
- 8) Bondarouk, T., Parry, E., & Furtmueller, E. (2017). Electronic HRM: four decades of research on adoption and consequences. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 28(1), 98-131. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2016.1245672>
- 9) Bondarouk, T. V., & Ruel, H. J. (2009). Electronic Human Resource Management: challenges in the digital era. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 20(3), 505-514.
- 10) Camisón-Haba, S., Clemente-Almendros, J. A., & Gonzalez-Cruz, T. (2019). How technology-based firms become also highly innovative firms? The role of knowledge, technological and managerial capabilities, and entrepreneurs’ background. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 4(3), 162-170.
- 11) Cerne, M., Jaklic, M., & Skerlavaj, M. (2013). Authentic leadership, creativity, and innovation: A multilevel perspective. *Leadership*, 9(1), 63-85. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1742715012455130>
- 12) Chege, S. M., Wang, D., & Suntu, S. L. (2020). Impact of information technology innovation on firm performance in Kenya. *Information Technology for Development*, 26(2), 316-345. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02681102.2019.1573717>
- 13) Chin, W. W., Marcolin, B. L., & Newsted, P. R. (2003). A partial least squares latent variable modeling approach for measuring interaction effects: Results from a Monte Carlo simulation study and an electronic-mail emotion/adoption study. *Information systems research*, 14(2), 189-217.
- 14) E-vahdati, S., Azar, N., & Shahreki, J. (2023). The Literature Landscape of Covid-19 and Socio-Economic Research: A Bibliometric Analysis. *Journal of Sustainability Science and Management*, 18(1), 1-21.
- 15) Ernsting, A., Schwarzer, R., Lippke, S., & Schneider, M. (2013). Relationship between health climate and affective commitment in the workplace. *International Journal of Health Promotion and Education*, 51(4), 172-179. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14635240.2012.758886>
- 16) Escrig-Tena, A. B., Segarra-Ciprés, M., García-Juan, B., & Beltrán-Martín, I. (2018). The impact of hard and soft quality management and proactive behaviour in determining innovation performance. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 200(1), 1-14.
- 17) Farndale, E., Scullion, H., & Sparrow, P. (2010). The role of the corporate HR function in global talent management. *Journal of world business*, 45(2), 161-168.

The Effect of HRIS on Innovation Capability of HR Employee and the Moderating Role of Affective Commitment

- 18) Ferreira, J., Coelho, A., & Moutinho, L. (2020). Dynamic capabilities, creativity and innovation capability and their impact on competitive advantage and firm performance: The moderating role of entrepreneurial orientation. *Technovation*, 92-93(1), 102061. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2018.11.004>
- 19) Florkowski, G. W., & Olivas-Lujan, M. R. (2006). The diffusion of human-resource information-technology innovations in US and non-US firms. *Personnel Review*, 35(6), 684-710.
- 20) Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *Journal of marketing research*, 18(1), 39-50.
- 21) Forsman, H. (2011). Innovation capacity and innovation development in small enterprises. A comparison between the manufacturing and service sectors. *Research policy*, 40(5), 739-750.
- 22) Francis, H., Parkes, C., & Reddington, M. (2014). E-HR and international HRM: a critical perspective on the discursive framing of e-HR. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 25(10), 1327-1350. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2013.870309>
- 23) Galanaki, E., Lazazzara, A., & Parry, E. (2019, 2019//). A Cross-National Analysis of E-HRM Configurations: Integrating the Information Technology and HRM Perspectives. *Organizing for Digital Innovation*, Cham.
- 24) García-Cruz, J., Real, J. C., & Roldán, J. L. (2018). Managerial perceptions of employees' affective commitment and product innovation. *Economics of Innovation and New Technology*, 27(3), 290-305. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10438599.2017.1346163>
- 25) Gellatly, I. R., & Withey, M. J. (2012). Organisational trust, affective commitment and bureaucratic control. *Journal of Trust Research*, 2(1), 31-52. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21515581.2012.659936>
- 26) Gurusinghe, R. N., Arachchige, B. J. H., & Dayarathna, D. (2021). Predictive HR analytics and talent management: a conceptual framework. *Journal of Management Analytics*, 8(2), 195-221. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23270012.2021.1899857>
- 27) Haepf, T. (2021). New technologies and employee well-being: the role of training provision. *Applied Economics Letters*, 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504851.2021.1922579>
- 28) Hair, J. F., Risher, J. J., Sarstedt, M., & Ringle, C. M. (2019). When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM. *European Business Review*, 31(1), 2-24. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-11-2018-0203>
- 29) Hashemi, S., Jasim Mohammed, H., Singh Dara Singh, K., Abbasi, G., & Shahreki, J. (2023). Exploring the effects of place attachment and positive emotions on place satisfaction and intentional behaviour in Iranian ski resort: a perspective from SOR model. *Journal of Sport & Tourism*, 27(2), 161-186.
- 30) Heidenreich, S., & Talke, K. (2020). Consequences of mandated usage of innovations in organizations: developing an innovation decision model of symbolic and forced adoption. *AMS Review*, 10(3-4), 279-298.
- 31) Holden, R. J., & Karsh, B.-T. (2010). The technology acceptance model: its past and its future in health care. *Journal of biomedical informatics*, 43(1), 159-172.
- 32) Hughes, D. J., Lee, A., Tian, A. W., Newman, A., & Legood, A. (2018). Leadership, creativity, and innovation: A critical review and practical recommendations. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 29(5), 549-569. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2018.03.001>
- 33) Hussain, Z., Wallace, J., & Cornelius, N. E. (2007). The use and impact of human resource information systems on human resource management professionals. *Information & Management*, 44(1), 74-89. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2006.10.006>
- 34) Ibrahim, N. F., Hasan, N. H. M., Rusli, P. N. A., Shahreki, J., & Hasim, M. A. (2022). Technology Acceptance Model in E-Wallet Adoption Among Generation Z Students: The Covid-19 Endemic Phase in Malaysia. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Technology and Innovation*, 4(4), 30-39.
- 35) Ibrahim, N. F., Said, A.-M. A., Abas, N., & Shahreki, J. (2020). Relationship between well-being perspectives, employee engagement and intrinsic outcomes: A literature review. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(12), 69-74.
- 36) Jiakui, C., Abbas, J., Najam, H., Liu, J., & Abbas, J. (2023). Green technological innovation, green finance, and financial development and their role in green total factor productivity: Empirical insights from China. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 382, 135131.
- 37) Johnson, R. D., Lukaszewski, K. M., & Stone, D. L. (2016). The evolution of the field of human resource information systems: Co-evolution of technology and HR processes. *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, 38(1), 28-43.
- 38) Khan, T. I., Jam, F. A., Akbar, A., Khan, M. B., & Hijazi, S. T. (2011). Job involvement as predictor of employee commitment: Evidence from Pakistan. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 6(4), 252-262.

The Effect of HRIS on Innovation Capability of HR Employee and the Moderating Role of Affective Commitment

- 39) Kleis, L., Chwelos, P., Ramirez, R. V., & Cockburn, I. (2012). Information technology and intangible output: The impact of IT investment on innovation productivity. *Information systems research*, 23(1), 42-59.
- 40) Klimovskikh, N., Sekerin, V., Makushkin, S., Kuzmicheva, A., Leontev, M., & Kochetkov, E. (2023). Impact of human resource management on improving the innovation potential of an enterprise to achieve the principles of sustainable development. *Journal of Law and Sustainable Development*, 11(1), e0274-e0274.
- 41) Lee, A., Legood, A., Hughes, D., Tian, A. W., Newman, A., & Knight, C. (2020). Leadership, creativity and innovation: a meta-analytic review. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 29(1), 1-35.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1359432X.2019.1661837>
- 42) Lei, Y., Guo, Y., Zhang, Y., & Cheung, W. (2021). Information technology and service diversification: A cross-level study in different innovation environments. *Information & Management*, 58(6), 103432.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2021.103432>
- 43) Liang, H., Saraf, N., Hu, Q., & Xue, Y. (2007). Assimilation of enterprise systems: the effect of institutional pressures and the mediating role of top management. *MIS quarterly*, 59-87.
- 44) Lin, Z., Zhou, Z., Fang, Y., Vogel, D., & Liang, L. (2018). Understanding affective commitment in social virtual worlds: The role of cultural tightness. *Information & Management*, 55(8), 984-1004.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.im.2018.05.005>
- 45) Loor-Zambrano, H. Y., Santos-Roldán, L., & Palacios-Florencio, B. (2022). Relationship CSR and employee commitment: Mediating effects of internal motivation and trust. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 28(2), 100185. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iedeen.2021.100185>
- 46) Maamari, B. E., & Osta, A. (2021). The effect of HRIS implementation success on job involvement, job satisfaction and work engagement in SMEs. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*.
- 47) Manuelli, R. E., & Seshadri, A. (2014). Human capital and the wealth of nations. *American economic review*, 104(9), 2736-2762.
- 48) Marler, J. H., & Fisher, S. L. (2013). An evidence-based review of e-HRM and strategic human resource management. *Human resource management review*, 23(1), 18-36.
- 49) Marler, J. H., & Parry, E. (2016). Human resource management, strategic involvement and e-HRM technology. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 27(19), 2233-2253.
- 50) Matzler, K., & Renzl, B. (2007). Personality Traits, Employee Satisfaction and Affective Commitment. *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*, 18(5), 589-598. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783360601061528>
- 51) McGuirk, H., Lenihan, H., & Hart, M. (2015). Measuring the impact of innovative human capital on small firms' propensity to innovate. *Research policy*, 44(4), 965-976.
- 52) Mekler, E. D., Brühlmann, F., Tuch, A. N., & Opwis, K. (2017). Towards understanding the effects of individual gamification elements on intrinsic motivation and performance. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 71, 525-534.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.08.048>
- 53) Meyer, J. P., & Herscovitch, L. (2001). Commitment in the workplace: Toward a general model. *Human resource management review*, 11(3), 299-326.
- 54) Meyer, J. P., Stanley, D. J., Herscovitch, L., & Topolnytsky, L. (2002). Affective, continuance, and normative commitment to the organization: A meta-analysis of antecedents, correlates, and consequences. *Journal of vocational behavior*, 61(1), 20-52.
- 55) Mgammal, M. H., & Al-Matari, E. M. (2021). Survey data of coronavirus (COVID-19) thought concern, employees' work performance, employees background, feeling about job, work motivation, job satisfaction, psychological state of mind and family commitment in two middle east countries. *Data in Brief*, 34, 106661.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2020.106661>
- 56) Min, S., So, K. K. F., & Jeong, M. (2019). Consumer adoption of the Uber mobile application: Insights from diffusion of innovation theory and technology acceptance model. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 36(7), 770-783.
- 57) Ngai, E. W., Law, C. C., & Wat, F. K. (2008). Examining the critical success factors in the adoption of enterprise resource planning. *Computers in industry*, 59(6), 548-564.
- 58) Nguyen, T.-T., Shahreki, J., Van Hong, P., & Van Tung, N. (2021). Rural entrepreneurship in Vietnam: identification of facilitators and barriers. In *Rural Entrepreneurship and Innovation in the Digital Era* (pp. 159-178). IGI Global.
- 59) Nha Trang, N. T., Nguyen, T.-T., Pham, H. V., Anh Cao, T. T., Trinh Thi, T. H., & Shahreki, J. (2022). Impacts of Collaborative Partnership on the Performance of Cold Supply Chains of Agriculture and Foods: Literature Review. *Sustainability*, 14(11), 6462.
- 60) Noutsu, F. A., Kala Kamdjoug, J. R., & Fosso Wamba, S. (2017). Acceptance and use of HRIS and influence on organizational performance of SMEs in a developing economy: the case of Cameroon. *World Conference on Information Systems and*

The Effect of HRIS on Innovation Capability of HR Employee and the Moderating Role of Affective Commitment

Technologies,

- 61) Oman, S. K., Tumer, I. Y., Wood, K., & Seepersad, C. (2013). A comparison of creativity and innovation metrics and sample validation through in-class design projects. *Research in Engineering Design*, 24(1), 65-92.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00163-012-0138-9>
- 62) Park, O., Bae, J., & Hong, W. (2019). High-commitment HRM system, HR capability, and ambidextrous technological innovation. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 30(9), 1526-1548.
- 63) Parry, E. (2011). An examination of e-HRM as a means to increase the value of the HR function. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 22(05), 1146-1162.
- 64) Pierro, A., Raven, B. H., Amato, C., & Bélanger, J. J. (2013). Bases of social power, leadership styles, and organizational commitment. *International Journal of Psychology*, 48(6), 1122-1134.
- 65) Ramírez-Correa, P., Grandón, E. E., Alfaro-Pérez, J., & Painén-Aravena, G. (2019). Personality Types as Moderators of the Acceptance of Information Technologies in Organizations: A Multi-Group Analysis in PLS-SEM. *Sustainability*, 11(14), 1-15.
- 66) Ringle, C. M., Sarstedt, M., Mitchell, R., & Gudergan, S. P. (2020). Partial least squares structural equation modeling in HRM research. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 31(12), 1617-1643.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2017.1416655>
- 67) Roglinger, M., Poppelbu, J., & Becker, J. (2012). Maturity Models in Business Process Management. *Business Process Management Journal*, 18(2), 328-346.
- 68) Ruel, H., & Van der Kaap, H. (2012). E-HRM usage and value creation. Does a facilitating context matter? *German Journal of Human Resource Management*, 26(3), 260-281.
- 69) Ruel, H. J., Bondarouk, T. V., & Van der Velde, M. (2007). The contribution of e-HRM to HRM effectiveness. *Employee Relations*, 29(3), 280-291.
- 70) Sahay, S., & Walsham, G. (2017). Information Technology, Innovation and Human Development: Hospital Information Systems in an Indian State. *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities*, 18(2), 275-292.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/19452829.2016.1270913>
- 71) Sarooghi, H., Libaers, D., & Burkemper, A. (2015). Examining the relationship between creativity and innovation: A meta-analysis of organizational, cultural, and environmental factors. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 30(5), 714-731.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusvent.2014.12.003>
- 72) Schalk, R., Timmerman, V., & den Heuvel, S. v. (2013). How strategic considerations influence decision making on e-HRM applications. *Human resource management review*, 23(1), 84-92.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2012.06.008>
- 73) Shahreki, J. (2019a). Electronic human resource management and employee efficiency: test of the mediating role of impersonal trust. *Journal of Soft Computing and Decision Support Systems*, 6(4), 20-29.
- 74) Shahreki, J. (2019b). The use and effect of human resource information systems on human resource management productivity. *Journal of Soft Computing and Decision Support Systems*, 6(5), 1-8.
- 75) Shahreki, J. (2024a). The assessment of users acceptance toward implementing human resource information system (HRIS). *International Journal of Business Information Systems*, (Article in Press).
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJBIS.2022.10049792>.
- 76) Shahreki, J. (2024b). E-HRM Delivers Better HRM Services. *International Journal of Services and Operations Management*, (Article in Press). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJSOM.2022.10052300>.
- 77) Shahreki, J. (2024c). High-performance work systems and HR efficiency: The mediating role of HRIS potentialities. *International Journal of Management and Decision Making*, 23(3), 290-310.
<https://doi.org/10.1504/IJMDM.2024.138313>
- 78) Shahreki, J., Chin, A. L. L., Jamaluddin, H., Shahraki, A., Nguyen, T. T., & Mand, A. A. (2023). The effect of technology readiness on technology acceptance in the electronic human resources management field. *International Journal of Business Information Systems*, 43(1), 74-86. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1504/IJBIS.2023.131085>
- 79) Shahreki, J., Ganesan, J., & Nguyen, T.-T. (2020). Personality traits and individual performance: test of the mediating role of motivation among top management. *International Journal of Business Governance and Ethics*, 14(3), 225-249.
<https://doi.org/10.1504/IJBGE.2020.108087>
- 80) Shahreki, J., Ganesan, J., & Nguyen, T.-T. (2021). The relationship between personality traits and individual performance: a case study in Malaysian hotel industry. *International Journal of Business Excellence*, 24(1), 101-124.
<https://doi.org/10.1504/IJBEX.2021.115368>
- 81) Shahreki, J., Ganesan, J., Raman, K., Chin, A. L. L., & Chin, T. S. (2019). The effect of human resource information system

The Effect of HRIS on Innovation Capability of HR Employee and the Moderating Role of Affective Commitment

- application on employee satisfaction and turnover intention. *Entrepreneurship and Sustainability issues*, 7(2), 1462-1479. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.9770/jesi.2019.7.2\(47\)](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.9770/jesi.2019.7.2(47))
- 82) Shahreki, J., & Ghanad, A. (2023). A Mediated Moderation Analysis of The Efficacy of E-HRM. *Proceeding of International Conference on Digital Advance Tourism, Management and Technology 2023*, 1(1), 30-47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.56910/ictmt.v1i1.12>
- 83) Shahreki, J., Jamaluddin, H., Chin, A. L. L., Hashemi, S., & Nakanishi, H. (2020). An examination on the effects of technology acceptance model in electronic human resource management. *Journal of Soft Computing and Decision Support Systems*, 7(3), 23-31.
- 84) Shahreki, J., & Lee, J. Y. (2024). Adopting human resource information system and work-related outcomes in emerging market SMEs: unified theory of acceptance and use of technology. *Cross Cultural & Strategic Management*, 31(1), 116-142. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CCSM-09-2022-0144>
- 85) Shahreki, J., Ling, T. S., Ibrahim, N. F., Chin, A. L. L., Jayiddin, N. F., & Ai, Y. J. (2022). The effect of big five personality traits on social network usage among the young generation. *International Journal of Business Excellence*, 26(3), 378-397. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJBEX.2020.10029666>
- 86) Shahreki, J., & Nakanishi, H. (2016). The relationship between task technology fit and individual performance: case study in hotel industry in Malaysia. *Journal of Soft Computing and Decision Support Systems*, 3(6), 1-15.
- 87) Shahreki, J., Nakanishi, H., Jayiddin, N. F., & Ibrahim, N. F. (2020). Technology and the HR field: The growth of human resource information systems. *Journal of Soft Computing and Decision Support Systems*, 7(2), 7-18.
- 88) Shahreki, J., Raman, K., Chin, A. L. L., Gowindasamy, M., Hashemi, S., & Ibrahim, N. F. (2024). E-HRM practices and HR service quality. *International Journal of Productivity and Quality Management*, (Article in Press). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJPQM.2023.10060633>.
- 89) Shin, D., Woodwark, M. J., Konrad, A. M., & Jung, Y. (2022). Innovation strategy, voice practices, employee voice participation, and organizational innovation. *Journal of Business Research*, 147, 392-402. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.04.015>
- 90) Squalli, J., & Wilson, K. (2014). Intelligence, creativity, and innovation. *Intelligence*, 46(1), 250-257. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intell.2014.07.005>
- 91) Stone, D. L., Deadrick, D. L., Lukaszewski, K. M., & Johnson, R. (2015). The influence of technology on the future of human resource management. *Human resource management review*, 25(2), 216-231.
- 92) [Record #24 is using a reference type undefined in this output style.]
- 93) Straub, D., Limayem, M., & Karahanna-Evaristo, E. (1995). Measuring system usage: Implications for IS theory testing. *Management science*, 41(8), 1328-1342.
- 94) Strohmeier, S. (2007). Research in e-HRM: Review and implications. *Human resource management review*, 17(1), 19-37.
- 95) Strohmeier, S. (2020). Smart HRM—a Delphi study on the application and consequences of the Internet of Things in Human Resource Management. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 31(18), 2289-2318.
- 96) Tang, W.-G., & Vandenberghe, C. (2020). Is affective commitment always good? A look at within-person effects on needs satisfaction and emotional exhaustion. *Journal of vocational behavior*, 119, 103411. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2020.103411>
- 97) Troshani, I., Jerram, C., & Hill, S. R. (2011). Exploring the public sector adoption of HRIS. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 111(3), 470-488.
- 98) Wright, P. M., & McMahan, G. C. (2011). Exploring human capital: putting 'human' back into strategic human resource management. *Human resource management journal*, 21(2), 93-104.
- 99) Xie, X., Wang, H., & García, J. S. (2021). How does customer involvement in service innovation motivate service innovation performance? The roles of relationship learning and knowledge absorptive capacity. *Journal of Business Research*, 136, 630-643. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.08.009>
- 100) Zhang, W., Xu, F., & Sun, B. (2020). Are open individuals more creative? The interaction effects of leadership factors on creativity. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 163, 110078. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2020.110078>
- 101) Zhang, Y., Xi, W., & Xu, F. Z. (2022). Determinants of employee innovation: an open innovation perspective. *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, 31(1), 97-124. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19368623.2021.1934933>
- 102) Zweifel, P. (2021). Innovation in health care through information technology (IT): The role of incentives. *Social Science & Medicine*, 289, 114441. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2021.114441>